

Genetic variability in leaf area and chlorophyll content of aromatic rice

U.K. Bansal, R.G. Saini, and A. Kaur, Department of Genetics, Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Ludhiana 141004, India

Commonly grown varieties of aromatic rice are poor yielders compared with nonaromatic dwarf varieties. To improve their yields, the incorporation of superior and physiologically efficient rice genotypes with stable high-quality grain production under local environments is necessary. Differences in canopy color and appearance of aromatic rice are conspicuous and reflect variation in chlorophyll content and leaf area, two important traits that might affect sink development in crop plants. This study reports on variation in leaf area and chlorophyll content of some aromatic landraces.

We grew 26 aromatic rice varieties and a nonaromatic high-yielding cultivar, IET8585, in a randomized block design with three replications in 2-m-long paired rows in PAU fields in 1996 kharif. A row-to-row distance of 30 cm and plant-to-plant distance of 10 cm were maintained. Standard agronomic practices were followed. Leaf area (cm²) and chlorophyll content were recorded for each entry at mid-anthesis stage. Actual leaf area was recorded using a portable leaf area meter (LI-COR, Model LI-3000A). Chlorophyll content was estimated following the method of Anderson and Boardman (1964): 100 mg of fresh leaf sample was crushed in 5 mL of 80% acetone and the extract was centrifuged for 10 min at 1000 rpm. Absorbency of supernatant was recorded at 645 and 663 nm in a CL-24 spectrophotometer. Chlorophyll content (expressed as mg g⁻¹ of a sample) was estimated as follows:

Chlorophyll a:

$$[12.7 (A_{663}) - 2.69 (A_{645})] V/1000 \times W$$

Chlorophyll b:

$$[22.9 (A_{645}) - 4.86 (A_{663})] V/1000 \times W$$

Total chlorophyll:

$$[20.2 (A_{645}) + 8.02 (A_{663})] V/1000 \times W$$

Aroma was determined using Siddiq's method (1991). The nonaromatic stocks, stocks with mild aroma, and those

with strong aroma were given scores of 0, 1, and 2, respectively.

The analysis of variance indicated that differences between stocks were significant for leaf area, chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and total chlorophyll content. The table shows values for these traits along with aroma. Leaf area ranged from 722.4 cm² in Guinata to 3281.8 cm² in Bindli semidwarf mutant. Leaf area was greater in landraces than in cultivated varieties, indicating higher vegetative growth in

landraces. Total chlorophyll content ranged from 1.44 to 3.37 mg g⁻¹ of fresh leaf sample. Chlorophyll a ranged from 0.99 to 2.26 mg g⁻¹ and chlorophyll b from 0.41 to 1.14 mg g⁻¹. Chlorophyll content was independent of aroma.

Results indicated variability for all three traits that are important for the improvement of aromatic rice. High chlorophyll content associated with upright foliage and delayed senescence is a useful trait that may favor high yield.

Leaf area, chlorophyll content, and aroma of different rice varieties compared with the nonaromatic check.

Stock	Leaf area plant ⁻¹ (cm ²)	Total chlorophyll (mg g ⁻¹)	Chlorophyll a (mg g ⁻¹) ^a	Chlorophyll b (mg g ⁻¹) ^a	Aroma ^b
Basmati 372B	1627.2	1.44	1.01	0.41	1
NIRRI 750	1666.0	1.44	0.99	0.44	1
Dwarf Basmati	1275.5	1.73	1.16	0.56	2
Begami	966.6	2.11	1.46	0.63	2
Basmati 1	2109.8	2.12	1.46	0.65	1
Ghanal	1969.5	2.27	1.47	0.78	2
HKR 239	976.8	2.42	1.77	0.66	1
C1 Basmati	1614.5	2.43	1.67	0.74	2
S4	2317.8	2.46	1.70	0.74	1
IET2686	2236.3	2.52	1.82	0.67	2
Basmati 370	1454.8	2.54	1.74	0.77	2
Major Djambon	2822.6	2.54	1.74	0.77	2
Xiang geng deo	1431.9	2.56	1.71	0.88	2
Pak Basmati	2631.3	2.60	1.62	0.99	2
Basmati 1A	1874.2	2.63	1.81	0.80	2
Azucena	1384.3	2.77	1.89	0.88	2
SC747	1944.4	2.81	1.78	1.00	2
Bindli semidwarf mutant	3281.8	2.85	1.95	0.87	1
C463	2176.0	2.86	1.96	0.87	2
Du thom thai bin hai phong	2525.3	2.92	2.07	0.82	2
Dehradun Basmati	1486.5	2.93	2.06	0.84	2
Basmati 372A	1795.6	2.95	2.08	0.84	1
T3	2159.5	3.14	2.14	0.97	2
Dawag	2718.2	3.18	2.15	1.00	1
Guinata	722.4	3.26	2.09	1.14	2
Basmati 405	2752.9	3.28	2.26	0.98	2
Domsiah	1651.9	3.37	2.26	1.07	2
IET8585 (nonaromatic check)	1273.2	2.05	1.41	0.62	0
LSD	242.7	0.39	0.13	0.07	

^amg g⁻¹ = mg of chlorophyll content g⁻¹ of leaf sample. ^bRated using a scale of 0-2, where 0 = no aroma, 1 = mild aroma, and 2 = strong aroma.